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METHODOLOGY OF OPTIMIZING SPORTS AND HEALTH PROGRAMS THROUGH SCANDINAVIAN WALKING

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Annotation: *This article talks about the importance of Nordic walking in optimizing sports rehabilitation programs, its role in maintaining and strengthening public health, and the methodological features of popularizing this sport in our country.*

Key words: *physical education and sports, skeletal muscles, healthcare, Nordic walking, measurement tools, control tools, monitoring, implementation, control, complex, methodology.*

INTRODUCTION

Forming a healthy lifestyle in our society, creating conditions suitable for the population, especially the young generation, to regularly engage in physical education and mass sports, maintaining the health of the population using existing opportunities, increasing the level of physical fitness, the surplus that worries the world health ministry today weight, large-scale works aimed at prevention and rehabilitation of cardiovascular diseases are being carried out. In particular, the development of science in the Republic of Uzbekistan, conducting scientific research in any field and putting the obtained scientific results into practice are considered as the priority directions of the state policy today.

Decree No. DP-6097 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 29, 2020 "On approval of the concept of development of science until 2030" aimed at ensuring and monitoring the implementation of the tasks specified in this decree in various areas, and Decree No. DP-6099 dated October 30, 2020 "Healthy "Decree on measures for wide implementation of lifestyle and further development of mass sports", Decision no. DP-4063 of the head of our state dated December 18, 2018 "On measures to prevent non-communicable diseases, support a healthy lifestyle and increase the level of physical activity of the population", November 3, 2022 "On the system of personnel training and scientific research in the field of physical education and sports" to ensure the implementation of the decision No. DP-414 and the decision No. DP-5282 of November 5, 2021 "On measures for the further development of walking, running, mini-football, badminton, streetball and "Workout" sports", implementation of specific programs in the field of physical education and mass sports shows the need to implement Scandinavian style walking for different distances based on the "Healthy Lifestyle" platform (5 and 10 thousand steps) for all segments of the population using innovative technologies [1,2].

THE LEVEL OF STUDY OF THE PROBLEM

The analysis of the scientific and methodical literature on the topic showed that a number of scientists of our republic T.S. Usmanhodzhaev, I.A. Koshbakhtiev, Sh.Kh. Khankeldiev, R.S. Salamov, L.Z. Kholmurodov, I.I. Saidov and A.A. on the problems of physical education and rehabilitation in CIS countries. Gujalovsky, I.G. Dukalsky, T.G. Sulimova, V.P. Guba, O.B.

Seregina, V.A. Ermakov, A.N. Kainov and others are using the results of scientific research. A.A. Poletaeva on walking in the Scandinavian way, N.T. Stanisky, A.V. Volkov, E.A. Zemba, N.T. Stansky, A.A. Alekseenko, V.A. Koloshkina, O.B. Nikolskaya, T.V. Meskevich, T.E. Starovoytova, A.S. Radchenko, N.I. Privoznikova, I.A. Kubanov, E.V. Many researches have been carried out by Chistyakova et al.

THE PURPOSE OF THE RESEARCH

Taking into account the individual capabilities of the population, the main means of health and rehabilitation is to determine the level of physical fitness, develop exercises that are suitable for all age groups of the population, rehabilitate diseases and increase the level of physical fitness.

TASKS OF THE RESEARCH:

Development of a new innovative computer program that divides the indicators of physical fitness into 5 levels (excellent, high, medium, low, weak) and monitors the state of health through tests that determine the level of physical fitness and health, taking into account the age group and individual capabilities of the population.

Based on the physical condition of all layers of the population, development of a three-step (triple control) set of exercises aimed at strengthening the assistant and special physical fitness, improving the level of health, rehabilitation and creating a functional base for walking in the Scandinavian way.

Taking into account the anthropometric, morphofunctional and physical fitness indicators of the people who walk in the Scandinavian way, development of a methodology for training in the Scandinavian walking technique by including a set of special exercises performed with the help of movement games, gymnastics and Scandinavian sticks in three methodological blocks.

An innovative mobile application that determines walking speed, training level, exercise duration, number of repetitions, competition mode and recovery process for the Scandinavian walking innovative training program aimed at strengthening the health, functional development, rehabilitation and increasing the level of physical fitness of the population, and enables independent theoretical and practical mastery of the participants. development.

ORGANIZATION OF RESEARCH:

About two thousand residents from different regions of our Republic participated in the pedagogical research. All participants of the study were divided into three groups: young, middle-aged and elderly. The number of participants in all three groups was the same.

Taking into account these problems, we have developed a research design for the popularization of walking in the Scandinavian way using various innovative technologies, and we have used this methodology in practice.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND ITS DISCUSSION:

The analysis of scientific methodical literature and Internet resources on the popularization of the Nordic walking sport showed that in the available information, mainly pictures posted on the Internet were used to popularize the Nordic walking sport. Their main influence is only for young people who are active on the Internet. To solve this problem, we used several methods that are equally suitable for all (see Figure 1).

We divided and arranged the popularization of Scandinavian walking sport in our country as follows:

1. Development of the concept of population health research

- Development of a questionnaire to determine the knowledge of all levels of the population on Nordic walking sports
- Separation of segments of the population that follow a healthy lifestyle and are interested in walking in the Scandinavian way
- Development of Scandinavian walking methodology taking into account the results of this survey.

2. To open special pages in social networks to popularize and promote Nordic walking sport

- Open a channel called "Scandinavian walking" on the Telegram social network and post daily information about this sport.
- Open an account called "Scandinavian walking" on Instagram and Facebook social networks, increase the number of subscribers and constantly post information and videos about Scandinavian walking

3. Organization of educational seminars for the popularization of Scandinavian walking in the district, city and regions

- Organization of seminar trainings with all strata of the population in cooperation with the district, city and regional administration
- To introduce the method of providing information on the positive effects of the Scandinavian walking sport on the human body and teaching walking techniques
- Separation of segments of the population that follow a healthy lifestyle and are interested in walking in the Scandinavian way
- Development of Scandinavian walking methodology taking into account the results of this survey.

1 picture. The design of popularizing the Scandinavian walking sport among the population of our country.

4. To open special pages in social networks to popularize and promote the sport of Nordic walking

- Open a channel called "Scandinavian walking" on the Telegram social network and post daily information about this sport.
- Open an account called "Scandinavian walking" on Instagram and Facebook social networks, increase the number of subscribers and constantly post information and videos about Scandinavian walking

5. Organization of educational seminars for the popularization of Scandinavian walking in the district, city and regions

- Organization of seminar trainings with all strata of the population in cooperation with the district, city and regional administration
- To introduce the method of providing information on the positive effects of the Scandinavian walking sport on the human body and teaching walking techniques

6. Providing health centers, culture and recreation parks with Nordic walking sticks in order to ensure that all sections of the population can practice sports for free

- Providing 30 pairs of walking sticks to city cultural and recreation parks located in each regional center
- Installation of (GPS) devices for the purpose of permanent control of the sticks.

2 picture. Banner with general information about Scandinavian walking sport.

3. The difference between Nordic walking and other sports. This section of our Nordic walking overview banner clearly shows the difference between Nordic walking and cycling.
4. Scandinavian walking technique. In this section, brief information about the Scandinavian walking technique is given, the correct movement of the legs and hands, and the correct control methods of the Nordic walking sticks are clearly shown.
5. The positive effect of Scandinavian walking on the human body. In this section, it is explained exactly how Nordic walking affects which organ systems and how important Nordic walking is in the proper development of the body.

CONCLUSION:

Today, the deterioration of the health of the population of our country, especially cardiovascular diseases, excess weight, nervousness, and various chronic diseases, puts a number of demands on specialists working in the field of sports.

Although the Nordic walking sport is one of the most important sports in developed countries today, it is important to use the latest innovative technologies to popularize this sport in our country.

Increasing the level of physical development and general physical fitness of the population, as well as the use of new innovative technologies in the effective use of free time of all segments of the population, and the use of special methods in the popularization of Nordic walking, will allow maintaining and strengthening human health, which is the most important and dearest to everyone today.

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